

Assessment of the Effects of Sales Force Performance Evaluation on Effective and Efficient Sales Management of a Service Company: First Bank Nigeria Plc Exposition

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Abstract

An investigation was conducted to discover the effects of sales force performance evaluation on effective and efficient sales management of First Bank Nigeria Plc. The relationship between sales force performance evaluation and training as well as the relationship between sales force performance evaluation and motivation were the two specific objectives of the study. The population of study is 100 executive staff of First Bank Nigeria Plc in Enugu metropolis was purposively targeted in the study. For the validity of the instrument, the questionnaire was vetted by research professionals based on face validity in terms of relevance to the subject matter, objective of the study, coverage of the content areas, appropriateness of language usage and clarity of purpose. The value of the test of reliability is 0.930 which was conducted using Cronbach's alpha. Primary data was adopted for the study and data was analyzed using Pearson's Product Moment correlation coefficient using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS). Hypotheses revealed that there is a significant relationship between sales force performance evaluation and training of sales people ($r = 0.507, p < 0.05$). It was also revealed that sales force performance evaluation has a significant relationship with motivation of sales people ($r = 0.788, p < 0.05$). The conclusion is that there is a direct and positive relationship between sales force performance evaluation and both training and motivation. Researchers recommend that sales managers need to take the evaluation of salespeople seriously to be able to be accountable to management regarding the nature and personality of sales people they recruit.

Keywords: Sales force evaluation, Sales force management, Sales force training and Sales force motivation.

Introduction

Marketing is war (Nwosu and Nkamnebe, 2006) and striving for survival in the 21st century global markets, organizations must ensure serious commitment towards delivering superior value (Kotler and Keller, 2006) to their myriad of consumers and customers through efficient and effective management and sustenance of their scarce resources. In other words, they tend to manage their resources (man, money, material and machine) sustainably. Sure, management juxtapose their marketing arsenal to establish a win-win situation (Okolo, Uzor, Anuforo, Obikeze, Nebo and Okafor, 2015) as gone are the days when marketers are overtly impetuous concerning their customers. In service supply chain, human labour forms a significant component of the value delivery system and physical handling of a product yields to standardized procedures and controls in the supply chains (Sengupta, Heiser and Cook, 2008). The focus of efficiencies in service supply chains is on management of capacity, flexibility of resources, information flows, service performance and cash flow management.

Sales force in any company – big or small, manufacturing or service, is charged with generating product sales from assigned customers in different independent territories. However, the evolving selling environment today is much more complex, demanding significant changes in performance indicators, compensation, control and attainment of goal (Okeke, 2014).

The sales force industry has grown exponentially since the mid 1990s (Rahman, Zailani, Al-Mamun, Jan, Ameziane and Hazeed, 2015). Organisations are desperately seeking qualified people, while they are feeling the effects of downsizing, industry growth, voluntary attrition, and the onset of new product lines. There is a major effort to hire sales people or to retain those already employed. Performance evaluation criteria are characterized as among the most crucial factors used to determine a sales person's salary or wage, promotion, or termination (Caruth and Handlogten, 1997).

The purpose of sales force evaluation can never be underestimated if organisations wish to actualise their objectives of achieving customer satisfaction and loyalty. Sale force evaluation is simply measuring goals with results (Jobber and Lancaster, 2009). It is the sole responsibility of the sales manager to embark on

regular sales performance evaluation; and this is usually very germane but critical and difficult (Spiro, Rich and Stanton, 2008). Improving sales force performance and profitability require judicious evaluation of salespeople to discover those who require management training and motivation (Spiro et al., 2008). Igwe and Tamunoiyowuna (2016) state that “Performance is the accomplishment of a given task measured against known standards of accuracy, completeness, cost/efficiency, and speed and effectiveness”. According to the trio, improving the performance of sales force has a direct relationship with profitability. Management must meet higher profitability through sales force performance. And sequel to that, this study’s intent is to investigate the effect of evaluation of salespeople towards actualising the dreams of sales management in a given services providing organisation.

Statement of the Problem

Training, motivation and evaluation are not taken seriously by many organisations (Spiro, Rich and Stanton, 2008). The role of sales and marketing is becoming increasingly important to manufacturing and service firms. Unfortunately, most of these companies do not apply the theories of sales management to their sales operations. They usually rely on past experience or judgment. Sales management is a management process that involves planning, setting objectives, developing policies, procedures, strategies and tactics in order to organize, co-ordinate, direct, motivate, communicate, train, supervise, control and evaluate results of deliberately planned sales programmes (Bolt 1987). This study seeks to investigate the effects of sales force evaluation for effective and efficient sales management of a service company: a first bank study aim of the study in Nigeria.

Objectives of the Study

To achieve the aim of the study, the following objectives were used.

1. To determine the relationship between sales force performance evaluation and training of sales people.
2. To investigate the relationship between sales force performance evaluation and motivating sales people.

Research Questions

1. What is the relationship between sales force performance evaluation and training of sales people?
2. What is the relationship between sales force performance evaluation and motivating sales people?

Research Hypotheses

1. Sales force performance evaluation has no significant relationship with training of sales people.
2. Sales force performance evaluation has no significant relationship with motivating sales people.

Significance of the Study

First of all, the study will benefit human resource and sales managers as they will gain adequate knowledge on the why their recruits perform poorly or handsomely in selling. Knowledge will also be acquired on the various evaluation dimensions. They will also discover that there is need to train and motivate workers to improve their performance. The salespeople will also be informed on management basis and reasons for performance evaluation. And this will guide their consciousness on how to perform their duties and responsibility with utmost diligence both presently and in the near future. Research students, lecturers, captains of industries and research organisations will use this repository to generate literature as well as data to guide the in further and future studies relevant to their fields.

Scope of Study

This research work will be confined to assessing the effects of the relevance of sales force evaluation in First Bank as a service company. This study will identify the available sales force evaluation tools, the ones used differently or otherwise by the company, and proffer the way forward. However, lack of adequate time and finance will not permit the extension of the study to their head offices, but it is believed that what will be obtained from their South-East branch offices will represent the general true situation.

Review of Related and Relevant Literature

Introduction

This section tries to look at studies that have been done in the area of sales management, sales force evaluation and the relevance of such evaluations.

Sales Force Management

The sales force has to be economically managed to perform optimally (Agbonifoh, Ogwo, Nnolim and Nkamnebe, 2007). "Sales management can, therefore, be considered to be the management activities of planning, organizing, staffing and evaluation as they relate to the sales force," (Okolo et al, 2015; Agbonifoh et al., 2007) Obi (2003) and Obikeze (2012) remark that the search for greater efficiency and effectiveness in the management theories is called sales force management. Sales force management is the sum total of all strategies and schemes employed in order to draw forth the interest, support efficiency and effectiveness of the salesman to fulfil organizational sales objectives. Therefore, in a very broad perspective, sales force management style may not differ significantly from those employed in other segments of an organization. Organizational management style is of prime importance in gauging the degree to which individuals apply themselves wholly or partly towards the realization of the organizational goals. Management is one of the most important human activities that permeate all organizations. For people to work together for the attainment of a predetermined objective there is always a need for management that is charged with the responsibility of ensuring that the aims and objectives of the organizations are realized.

American Institute of Management identified that management is used to designate either a group of functions or the personnel who carry them out, hierarchy or the activities of men who compose it, to provide antonym to either labour or ownership. Obi (2003) and Obikeze (2012) add that management is seen as getting things done through the effort of others. Management can be more scientifically defined as the co-ordination of all the resources of an organizing, directing and controlling in order to attain organizational objectives. Management is the process of allocating an organizational input (human and material resources) by planning, organizing, directing and controlling to the purpose of producing outputs (goods and services), desired by its customers so that organizational objectives are accomplished. The systems approach to management encourages management to perceive the internal and external environmental factors as an integrated whole.

Quick transmission of information to all work group/employees such as the sales force can simultaneously stop the spread of harmful rumours, reduce the impact or incidence of bad news, or increase the incidence or impact of good news, reduce channel conflict, minimize job dissatisfaction, etc (Okolo et al., 2015). An organization would perform better when its personnel's function as a team, that is, as members of highly effective work group. A work group can be defined as two or more people interacting and inter-dependent, who have the ability to behave in a unified manner with a shared purpose or objective in mind (Agbonifoh, et al, 2007).

Sales Force Management Functions

Okolo et al. (2015) and Armstrong (2001) identify the following functions of sales management:

Selling: Sales representative know that art of "salesmanship", approaching, presenting, answering objections and closing sales. Managers organize sales efforts, both within and outside their companies.

Prospecting: The sales representative or the manager is a key contact with customer and other bodies. He is also responsible for the building and maintaining of an effective distribution network for the company's product(s).

Servicing: Sales managers provide service to customers consulting on their problems, rendering technical assistance, arranging, financing and expediting delivery.

Information Gathering: Sales managers and representatives carry out market research and intelligence work and also fill in call reports from time to time.

Allocating: Sales representatives evaluate customer quality and allocate scarce products during shortages. He also makes critical marketing decisions such as budgeting, quotas and territories. A sales manager also participates in decision making on products, distribution policies, channel selections and pricing.

Sales Force Performance Evaluation

Sales force performance evaluation is the last function of the sales management process (Kerin, Hartley and Rudelius, 2011). It is the interval when sales management correlate objectives with performance and profit. It helps in the sales manager in identifying and sieving or fishing out dull and low performing salesperson from smart and high performing ones; and taking adequate measures to praise, reward and promote the astute and diligent salesperson and also, either advising, educating, guiding, training, punishing and totally removing the lackadaisical one (Jobber, Lancaster and Jamieson, 2004). Sales force evaluation is assessing result of sales force activities with the results (Jobber and Lancaster, 2009). In evaluating the performance

of salespeople, both quantitative and qualitative methods are adopted. But first of all, describing a model of sales force evaluation process is necessary.

According to Jobber and Lancaster (2009) it starts with setting the objectives that sales force and sales management intent to achieve as part of the major marketing and business plan. The objectives is pivoted on financial focus and include revenue generation for the company, expected profit, level of customer services, good customer cooperation and relationships, amount of fund to be expended, share of market needed and achievable level of customer satisfaction. Secondly, the firm then defines and determines the viable and robust strategies to be adopted to bring the sales management objectives to fruition. The strategy could define the number of salespeople to be recruited, the number, location and size of the territories, the number and size of accounts to serve, the product, brand and product lines to market, means of reaching the customers, training, motivation and compensation plan to be adopted. All these can be broken down into simpler and specific strategies and tactics aimed at ensuring that the company doesn't derail from the main fact; customer satisfaction at a sustainable profit. Also, performance standards are set relating to the company, customers, products, regions and the salespeople. Then, the need to assess results of sales performance in accordance with set objectives follows and finally, deliberate and resounding activities and actions are taken to ensure gainful improvement in sales performance.

In addition, evaluation proper takes two aspects such as the quantitative and qualitative performance evaluation dimensions. In quantitative dimension, the sales plan spells out assessment based on input and output measures. In Jobber and Lancaster (2009; Spiro et al., 2008; Kerin et al., 2011; Jobber et al., 2004) the following are the output measures spelt out for the individual salespeople:

- Sales revenue achieved
- Profit generated
- Percentage gross profit margin achieved
- Sales per potential account
- Sales per active account
- Sales revenue as a percentage of sales potential
- Number of orders
- Sales to new customers
- Number of new customer

Similarly and on the other hand, the input measures would include the following:

- Number of calls made
- Calls per active account
- Number of calls on prospects
- Call for potential account
- Number of quotations

In qualitative dimension, evaluation of salespeople's performance is conducted more on a subjective manner during field visits. It involves skills in selling such as handling the opening and developing rapport, quality of sales presentation, identification of the needs of customers, use of visual aids, ability to overcome objections and ability to close sales. Also, customer relationship is evaluated to discover the salesperson's creativity in attracting and cooperating with the customers to foster acceptance. How professional is the salesperson in addressing customer complaints is also very necessary here as it has serious implication to the entire sales plan and programmes. Self organisation is also needed to discover how diligent the salesperson is with making call preparations, embarking on effective and efficient travels, keeping customer records up-to-date, relaying customer information to the management at the headquarters and conducting self-analysis of performance to improve weakness. In the same vein, the salesperson's knowledge of the product comes to light. He must gain adequate information and knowledge about the benefits the company's products and that of competitors could offer customers. As well as the strengths and weaknesses of the product he represent have over that of the competitors. And finally, the salesperson requires to cooperate with and project

positive attitude towards the overall company objectives; and also cooperate with suggestions and changes identified and made during training for improved sales

Furthermore, sales force evaluation is very significant in the life of any business organisation. It aids in hiring and firing high performing and low or poor performing sales executives. It helps in allocating salespeople to required territories and also supports in enhancing their productivity through customer and product lines call patterns (Kesari, 2014). The existence of organisation is to achieve competitive advantage through efficient performance of employees in such organisations. Therefore, it has become an established part of administration convention that there should be an avenue by which performance should be measured, monitored and controlled (Bratton & Gold, 2003). Evaluation is a system that provides vital data for logical, objectives and competent decision making aimed at recuperating performance, identifying training needs, managing careers and setting levels for reward and for legal purposes. This ensures that there is a move away from using it for identifying future potential, improving current performance, allocating rewards and career planning to performance evaluation used as an effective tool in identifying strength and weaknesses of employees and ways of using the strength to the advantage of the organisation in order to overcome the weakness (David, 2013).

Sales Force Evaluation: Nigerian Banking Sector Experience

The banking sector plays a vital role in the development of the economy, therefore a need for effective leadership and management style to achieve performance is fundamental. Okolo et al. (2015) note that for any organization to be successful in achieving its objectives and increase productivity in the global competitive market, it must engage in good and effective management style to improve organisational performance. Ojokuku, Odetayo and Sajuyigbe (2012), attests that efficient leadership is a determinant of success especially in Nigerian banks. Different leaders have different management style that prove to be closely related with their organisational performance and output and are transformational and transactional style of leadership.

According to Hartog, Muijen and Koopman (1997) these two types of leadership styles have gained ground and attention in the Nigerian banking. It is also argued that they are both interrelated in any organisation to produce outcomes such as job satisfaction, group performance, employee performance and organisational commitment. Luchak and Gellatly (2007) remark that employee commitment is positively related with work effort and negatively with absenteeism and employee turnover.

Another aspect is the gender differences in the Nigerian banking sector, According to William and Bedward (2001), there is no difference between male and female in problem solving abilities, analytical skill, competitive drive, motivation and learning ability and it was observed that women are more eager to obey the rules and have expectations of success than men. Recently in Nigeria there has been significant change in terms of the increase in female participation rate in the work force and a rethinking of what composes male and female roles

which confirms what William earlier stated that there is no significance difference in male and female in job productivity while Iyiola (2011) shows there is a relationship between gender culture and performance in the Nigerian banking industry. Therefore it is necessary for organisations to create realistic pathways for effective utilization of all human resources.

Organisational Benefits of Sales Force Evaluation

Malcolm and Jackson (2002), summarize the benefits of performance evaluation to the organisation as the effective basis for retention of employees, reward decisions, targeted training based on identified needs and future employee promotion decisions. Schraeder and Lindsay (2006) suggest some additional benefits like identifying unproductive work practices, identifying potential problems, which are hindering the growth of the organisation and detecting talented employees and future leaders of the organisation. Conversely, Farmer and Van Dyne (2010), stress its need for updating personnel records, revisiting job description while Aldakhilallah and Parente (2002) discuss sales force evaluation benefits in terms of transfers. Behery and Patron (2008) assert that sales force evaluation helps the organisation to certify promotion and demotion.

Benefits to the Employee

Sales force evaluation takes record of an employee's past performance and compares it to the present and focuses on the improvement of the future (Bersin, 2008). By so doing, it gives employees the opportunity to

communicate their ideas, concerns and prospects for the overall goal of the organisation. Mullins (1999) states that ideally, performance evaluation helps the employee to receive feedback for their performance and evaluate their contributions to the common goal of the organisation. Also, Derven (1990) and Kuvaas (2006) review that sales force evaluation helps align employee performance to organisational goals. Weise and Buckley (1998) confirm that it also helps an employee to make personal decisions regarding his or her current performance and provide strategies for future development. This is in agreement with the assertions of David (2013) who believes that self-efficacy is an important factor for personal growth and development on the job. On the other hand, Nelson (2000) adds that performance evaluation basically helps the employee to have a purpose and set approach in the direction of the target goal elaborating that appraisal system acts like a motivator for the employee who performs well in the present to keep the achievement up and in the future.

Motivation of Sales Force

The adequate motivation of an organization's sales force is very profitable to the marketing success of such organization (Okolo, Uzor, Anuforo, Obikeze, Nebo and Okafor, 2015; Coughlan and Narasimhan, 1992). Motivation of a company's sales force has been seen as a very delicate phenomenon for managers and management generally (Anca-Mihaela, 2013). It is what makes an individual to be resilient, determined and dogged in the face of difficult and risky working situations. That is because it initiates a glimpse of hope at various troubling working conditions. According to him, motivation is anchored in need, drive and goal. Uduji and Nnabuko (2008) define motivation "as psychological forces that determine the direction of a person's behaviour in an organization, a person's level of effort, and a person's level of persistence in the face of obstacles." Jobber and Lancaster (2009), assert that critical understanding of salespeople as individual with unique traits will ensure effective motivation strategy. Akanbi (n.d) defines motivation as "a process that starts with a physiological deficiency or need that activates behaviour or a drive that is aimed at a goal incentive." Motivation constitutes those things which when put in place propels a worker to behave in a desired manner in the work environment" (Onodugo, 2000). He states that motivation is a difficult managerial phenomenon as the needs of individuals vary among themselves and also vary even within a particular individual at different or even similar work situations. Anca- Mihaela (2013) supports this statement and then states that "sales practices and operations are likely to be different and as a result management will be challenged to find the best way to motivate global sales personnel." Workers who are adequately motivated will put in more effort towards the achievement of organizational goal. In other words, workers will put in their best when they are judiciously motivated. That is, motivation becomes the spur of the moment to expedite work and performance. That is because he sees himself as part and parcel of the entity.

There are different channels through which individuals or groups can be motivated. It could be through financial incentive; salary (Amue and Igwe, 2014), commission, bonus, promotion to a higher management cadre, special recognition for outstanding performance, etc. Gunu (2010) asserts that "most companies focus on financial motivation, but public recognition, sales contests and simple personal recognition for a job well done can be highly effective in encouraging greater sales effort". Onodugo (2000) notes four motivation techniques: money, reinforcement, participation and job enrichment.

Jobber and Lancaster (2009; Spiro, 2008) note some factors capable of motivating salespeople: Individual meeting with supervisor to discuss career, job problems, regular accomplishment in the field by the sales manager; 'merit' promotion system rather than 'dead man's shoes', participating in setting sales target, sales force meetings/conventions', sales contest/competitions, bigger car for higher sales turnover and fear of dismissal/unemployment.

Moreover, Ugwu and Coker (2012) classify incentive into the following categories: cash incentives, special benefits, recognition, special opportunities, piece rate, commission, profit sharing, gain-sharing, golden handcuffs (sometimes called retention or loyalty incentives), and share ownership.

Amue, Asiegbu and Chukwu (2012) conducted a study on 'Improving Sales Performance through Sales Force Motivation Strategies: A Study of Pharmaceutical Firms in Nigeria' and discovered that there exist a robust relationship between motivation and sales performance. Pragmatically, salespeople's performances grow exponentially through improved motivation by management. In their study, Ugwu and Coker (2012)

discovered that incentive schemes have high significant relationship with employee motivation in organisations. In their research which anchored on the Nigerian education sector, Ulabor, Chima and Hakeem (2014) discovered that the dominating motivation techniques include providing better financial benefits, promotion, medical, job security etc.

Sales Force Training

Organisations need to attain substantial growth and development in order to extricate itself from the danger of going under. And to surety this perpetual and enduring life span, training is a veritable input (Igwe and Tamunoiyowuna, 2016). Training can engender enormous reward for an organization (Rahman, 2015). Training of salespersons is indisputable in an organization (Abeysekera and Jayakody, 2011). Sales force success is embedded in training (Krishnamoorthy, Misra and Prasad, 2005). A company's sales force need to be properly trained to know how to make effective sales presentations. They need to know their numerous customers and how to serve them. They need to know their customers' needs, motive and buying habits. They are tutored in art of identifying profitable customers and also the unprofitable one as well as taught the skills required to produce sound sales report. "Sales force training can be defined as a planned process to modify attitude, knowledge or skill through continuous learning experience, consistent coaching and feedback to all sales representatives to achieve effective performance in their sales activity in order to increase organizational performance/profitability. It also refers to the planned attempt by an organization to facilitate employee learning of job related knowledge, skills and behaviours" (Okeke, 2014).

Training emphasizes acquainting potential sales persons with the requisite skill that will support them in performing their sales responsibility diligently and tenaciously (Uduji and Nnabuko, 2008). A company's sales force needs to be indoctrinated with the corporate culture of the organization they represent. The need to know the company's products, their suppliers, their competitor, their target customers as well as the territory they have to give coverage. Most companies shy away from training their sales force because of the financial involvement. They are short sighted in the sense that they fail to recognize that a trained sales force will add a substantial value to the company's bottom line in the long run. Although

U.S. companies might spend billions of dollars annually in training salespeople, it ensure that salespeople understands the company's history and objective, its financial standing, its facilities, its products and markets (Kotler and Armstrong, 2001).

Jobber and Lancaster (2009) identify six components of a training programme:

1. The company- This has to do with the objective, policies and organization.
2. Its products.
3. Its competitors and their products.
4. Selling procedure and techniques.
5. Work organization and report preparation.
6. Relationship management.

They also throw light on the training methods which include: lecture, films, role playing, case studies, in-the-field training and e-learning.

Research Methodology

The study utilised survey method by administering structured questionnaire to gather primary data from select executives of First Bank. The scope of the study covered sales force performance evaluation, training and motivation of sales force in First Bank, Enugu metropolis. The population of the study was 100 executive staff of the bank who were purposively chosen. Content validity was used to determine the validity of the instrument by giving questionnaire to marketing experts who modified and made the necessary corrections so that the instrument can be justifiable. Reliability was done and the value is 0.930 which was conducted using Cronbach's Alpha which indicated an internal consistency of the instrument. Analysis of data was done using Pearson's Product Moment correlation coefficient using Statistical Package for Social Sciences.

Hypotheses Testing

The hypothesis for the study was

- Sales force performance evaluation has no significant relationship with training of sales people.
- Sales force performance evaluation has no significant relationship with motivating sales people.

Hypothesis One

➤ Sales force performance evaluation has no significant relationship with training of sales people. This hypothesis was tested using the Pearson’s product moment correlation technique and the following results were produced.

Table 1 Correlation between sales force performance evaluation and training of sales people

		Evaluation	Training
Evaluation	Pearson Correlation	1	.507
	Sig. (1-tailed)		.123
	N	96	96
Training	Pearson Correlation	.507	1
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.123	
	N	96	96

Source – Researchers analysis, 2018.

The results are presented in a matrix which indicates the Pearson correlation coefficient, its significance and the sample size that the calculation is based on. In this result, the Pearson correlation coefficient, $r = 0.507$, and it is statistically significant ($p=0.123$). The direction of the relationship is positive i.e performance evaluation and training of sales persons are positively correlated meaning that the variables tend to increase together. The magnitude or strength of association is moderate ($.3 < r < .5$).

Decision – the results indicate that there is a significant relationship between the sales force performance evaluation and training of sales persons. Therefore the null hypothesis was rejected and the alternate hypothesis is accepted.

Hypothesis two

➤ Sales force performance evaluation has no significant relationship with the motivation of sales people.

This hypothesis was tested using the Pearson’s product moment correlation technique and the following results were produced.

Table 2. Correlation between sales force performance evaluation and the motivation of sales people

		Evaluation	Motivation
Evaluation	Pearson Correlation	1	.788
	Sig. (1-tailed)		.007
	N	96	96
Motivation	Pearson Correlation	.788	1
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.007	
	N	96	96

Source – Researchers analysis, 2018.

The results are presented in a matrix which indicates the Pearson correlation coefficient, its significance and the sample size that the calculation is based on. In this result, the Pearson correlation coefficient, $r = 0.788$, and it is statistically significant ($p=0.007$). The direction of the relationship is positive i.e sales force performance evaluation and motivation of sales persons are positively correlated meaning that the variables tend to increase together. The magnitude or strength of association is moderate ($.3 < r < .7$).

Decision – the results indicate that there is a significant relationship between the evaluation and motivation of sales persons. Therefore the null hypothesis was rejected and the alternate hypothesis is accepted.

Summary of Findings

Revelation of hypothesis depict a significant relationship between sales force performance evaluation and re-training of sales people ($r = 0.507$, $p < 0.05$). It was also revealed that sales force evaluation has a

significant relationship with motivation of sales people ($r = 0.788$, $p < 0.05$). And this is in line with Spiro et al. (2008) remark that evaluation of sales force has direct influence with training and motivation of sales personnel.

Conclusion

There is a direct and positive relationship between sales force performance evaluation and both training and motivation. Conducting performance evaluation would pinpoint salespeople's weaknesses such as lack of training and inadequate motivation. And when this is identified and corrected, performance would improve significantly.

Recommendations

Human resources and sales managers need to take the evaluation of sales people seriously to be able to be accountable to management regarding the nature and personality of sales people they recruit. In other words, management should not embark on rule-of-thumb in determining how salespeople perform. An empirical measure must be put in place to evaluate them. Evaluation is very significant in revealing a poor performing sales person to discover what is lacking. What is lacking might be that the sales person requires more training or that he needs to be motivated to bring him to the state of emotional, social and economic equilibrium to enable him perform his duty judiciously.

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